

Numerical Simulation and Analysis of the mass attenuation coefficient, half-value layer, and mean free path of X-rays at 30 keV in Fe, Ag, Sn, Pt, Au, and Pb using XCOM and FASST: Comparison Study by Matlab -2014

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Abstract- To characterize and analyze the capability of elements to attenuate X-rays, a number of important physical indicators were calculated, namely the mass attenuation coefficient μ/ρ , the half-value layer HVL, and the free path rate MFP, as they play a role in describing the nature of the material that can be used as a protection method in medical centers and laboratories related to dealing with X-rays, using two methods. The first is using the XCOM program, and the second method is the FFAST tool. They were applied to the elements Fe, Ag, Sn, Pt, Au, and Pb at an energy of 30 KeV, in order to evaluate the effectiveness of each element in medical and industrial applications related to radiation protection. We obtained good agreement between the two methods, and the Matlab program was relied upon in the calculations and drawings that show the relationship and agreement between them.

Keywords – Attenuation coefficient, HVL, MFP, X-ray.

I. INTRODUCTION

The mass and linear attenuation of X-rays μ/ρ , along with other shielding distinguishing features for example the half-value layer(HVL) and the free path rate(MFP), are important data in physics and many Other application areas. Therefore, knowing these properties is essential. In order to know the behavior of materials in advance, it is necessary to understand the behavior of materials by studying them in order to understand the behavior of the materials used in the manufacture of devices used in this field, especially medical devices, to protect workers and patients in treatment centers and hospitals. By studying these materials, we can understand their behavior and predict the quantity and concentration of these materials and their role in radiation protection [1,2]. To achieve a safe level of protection for materials used in gamma and x-ray applications, the materials used to shield these rays must have uniformity in density, composition, and the required thickness to absorb radiation, as well as a high atomic number.

Therefore, the basic values that define the scattering and absorption of X-ray and gamma ray photons in a material are the mass attenuation coefficient μ/ρ , electron density, effective atomic number Z_{eff} , half-layer value(HVL), and mean free path of the radiation(MFP)[3]. Since radiation attenuation is a

distinct and intrinsic property of materials, much research has been conducted to identify the ability of elements or compounds to attenuate and block radiation, This can be clarified by the following exponential decay equation: [4]:

$$\frac{I}{I_0} = e^{-\mu x} \quad (1)$$

I and I_0 represent the initial photon intensity and the photon intensity which passing through the material, respectively. While x represents the material thickness that is it through which the radiation passes, μ denotes the linear attenuation coefficient in units of square centimeters. Sometimes, it can be given as the mass attenuation coefficient divided by the material density, which is given in units of cm^2/g . The attenuation, or weakening, of radiation in a material depends on how its photons interact with the electrons, atoms, or molecules of the material upon which they fall. These processes are three: first processes photoelectric effect, second it is Compton scattering, and last pair production. May be interaction mechanisms have the Raleigh and Mie processes.

These interaction processes are distinguish by differing energy thresholds and high cross-sectional areas for different materials [5]. As mentioned earlier, half-value layer HVL and mean free path MFP are hallmarks of radiation shielding. Knowing and calculating their values allows us to more clearly identify and

predict the nature of radiation in various radiation measurement applications. Half-value layer HVL can be defined as the material thickness which used to attenuate or weaken and reduce the incident radiation intensity to half its value .It is given by relation:

$$HVL = \frac{\ln 2}{\mu} \dots (2)$$

Where μ linear attenuation coefficients [6,7,8]. Mean free path (MFP) is the average distance a photon which they travel along its path within the material before being absorbed. It is calculated from the following relationship[6,7,8,9,10]:

$$MFP = \frac{1}{\mu} \dots (3)$$

II. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To find the best method for calculating the X-ray attenuation coefficient for some elements with multiple programs and techniques, and to understand and distinguish this best method for obtaining close values for the attenuation coefficient, thus saving time and effort spent in determining the type and properties of the basic components of materials used in radiation shields and protection devices, we used in this research data from both the XCOM program and the FFAST tool to calculate the X-ray mass attenuation coefficients.

XCOM is a program affiliated with the US Atomic Energy Commission (NIST) through which we can be made an estimate of X-rays and gamma rays mass attenuation coefficients and gamma rays when they pass through elements, alloys, or compounds based on experimental data and accurate theoretical models at different energies. It is used in the fields of medical physics and engineering physics, as well as radiation protection. FFAST is a computational tool that relies primarily on mathematical models of absorption and radiation attenuation to estimate attenuation coefficients.

It is also used to evaluate the performance of materials in radiation protection and spectroscopic analysis, and is an experimental alternative to XCOM data. In this research, we calculated the mass absorption coefficient of iron-Fe, silver-Ag, tin-Sn, Platinum -Pt, gold-Au, and lead-Pb elements, as they are the most commonly used elements in designing shields and protection devices against X-rays in research centers, hospitals, and diagnostic clinics at an energy of 30 KeV using both the XCOM program and the FFAST tool. The values for each element were entered into the MATLAB program and drawn the relationship between the mass attenuation coefficient μ/ρ of all elements with their atomic numbers was. The relationship appeared as shown in Figure 1.

Fig.1: The dependence of the X- ray attenuation coefficient in Fe, Ag, Sn, Pt, Au, and Pb on atomic number of each element at 30 KeV.

To determine the extent of agreement between the two methods in arriving at the mass absorption coefficient of X-rays in these elements at the energy used (30 keV), we calculated the linear correlation coefficient between them by use matlab code $R = \text{corrcoef}(\mu_XCOM, \mu_FFAST);$ $r_value = R(1,2);$

Where r value represent the correlation coefficient , μ XCOM is the mass attenuation coefficient by XCOM program and μ FFAST is the mass attenuation coefficient by FFAST program . The value of the correlation coefficient ($r = 0.999$) is very nearly one, signifying a strong, positive linear relationship between the two methods. This means that the calculated values appeared very similar for both methods for all studied elements (Fe, Ag, Sn, Pt, Au, Pb).

Fig.2:Data points , ideal line (y=x)and fit line of mass attenuation coefficient dates of X ray in (Fe, Pt,Au,Pb,Ag,Sn)

Graphical analysis and statistical calculations were performed using MATLAB to determine the most appropriate method for representing the relationship between the calculated values and to evaluate the compatibility between the two programs as in Figure (1).

In Figure (2), we note the blue dots representing the actual values for each element. The horizontal axis represents the μ/ρ values from the XCOM program, while the vertical axis represents the corresponding values from FFAST. The dashed red line represents the ideal relationship ($y = x$), which represents a perfect match between the values. The solid green line denotes the linear fit of the actual data. The closeness to the ideal red line points and their coincidence with the red line indicates a good agreement between the XCOM and FFAST results. The differences between the values, which did not exceed 2% in most cases, are due to the two programs relying on very similar mathematical models to calculate the X-ray mass attenuation coefficient. These small differences between the values provided by the two programs are due to slight differences in the energy interpolation methods or the physical constants used in the calculations within each database, where the energy input values differ slightly.

Therefore, we approximated the energy values in FFAST by approximating them to the energy input values in XCOM. In short, through the analysis results using MATLAB, the existence of this high compatibility between the XCOM program and the FFAST tool confirms that the use of either of them as an accurate and reliable tool in applied studies for designing materials that protect against X-rays and in analyzing the radiation properties of materials in the spectral, industrial, medical, therapeutic and diagnostic fields. This agreement between these two programs appear clear in figure 2. Two figures 3 and 4 show the half-value layer HVL and the mean free path MFP of X-rays incident on the selected elements at 30 keV energy using equations 3 and 4 using the linear absorption coefficient extracted from the mass absorption coefficient μ/ρ , which was calculated once with the XCOM program and again with the FFAST tool, and using the element density.

This is done by multiplying the mass absorption coefficient extracted using the two methods mentioned by the density. From the two figures, we notice that the dependence of the half-value layer HVL on the atomic number was similar to the direction of the mean free path MFP, i.e., the two figures are considered a comparison of the half-value layer HVL and the mean free path MFP of X-rays penetrating these elements, where it appears that the highest value of the half-value layer HVL and the mean free path MFP was for the elements with the lowest atomic number than for the elements have the highest atomic number.

Fig3. HVL of X-ray in Fe, Ag, Sn, Pt, Au, and Pb versus atomic number of each element at 30 KeV.

Fig4. MFP of X-ray in Fe, Ag, Sn, Pt, Au, and Pb versus atomic number of each element at 30 KeV.

Table 1: Comparison between the values of mass attenuation coefficient μ/ρ (cm²/g), the half-value layer HVL (cm) and Mean free path MFP (cm) by XCOM and FFAST

element	Z	density (gm/cm ³)	μ/ρ (cm ² /g)		HVL (cm)		MFP (cm)	
			by XCOM	by FFAST	by XCOM	by FFAST	by XCOM	by FFAST
Fe	2	7.86	8.17	8.08	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
	6		6	58	08	09	56	57
Ag	4	10.4	36.6	36.8	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	7		8	79	18	18	26	26

Sn	50	7.3	41.21	40.9190	0.0023	0.0023	0.0033	0.0033
Pt	78	21.41	26.41	25.846	0.0012	0.0013	0.0018	0.0018
Au	79	18.85	27.52	26.9520	0.0013	0.0014	0.0019	0.0020
Pb	82	11.34	30.32	29.745	0.0002	0.0002	0.0003	0.0003

Table 1 shows atomic number of any element Z, density of each element (gm/cm³). The values obtained by the two methods for mass attenuation coefficient μ/ρ by units of (cm²/g), the half-value layer HVL and Mean free path MFP are in units are (cm).

III. CONCLUSION

From the table and figures 1,2,3 and 4, good agreement is shown between the mass attenuation coefficient values μ/ρ for X-rays at 30 keV obtained by both programs for the selected elements Fe, Ag, Sn, Pt, Au, and Pb. Also, agreement is shown that values of (HVL) and (MFP) calculated for each element. The highest values of the mass attenuation coefficient μ/ρ were found for tin (Sn), reaching (41.21, 40.9190) cm²/g from the XCOM program and the FFAST tool, respectively, while the values of HVL and MFP for lead were the same, reaching (0.0023, 0.0033) cm respectively, by both methods, which confirms the validity of the two methods used in the calculation and their compatibility, while the lowest value of μ/ρ was for the iron (Fe) element, reaching (8.176) cm²/g from the XCOM program and 8.0858 cm²/g from the FFAST tool, while the values of HVL were (0.0108, 0.0109) cm based on the using XCOM program outputs of the mass attenuation coefficient and the FFAST tool, respectively, while the values of MFP were (0.0156, 0.0157) cm also based on the using XCOM program outputs of the mass attenuation coefficient and the FFAST tool, respectively. This indicates the role of the atomic number in attenuating X-rays, which can be summarized as follows: It is assumed that when the atomic number of the element used in the shielding method is higher, the attenuation of these rays is greater. This is what was observed for the elements Fe, Pt, Au, and Pb. However, it was noted that the attenuation coefficient of tin (Sn) and silver (Ag) is higher than that of lead (Pb). This is maybe due to the higher density of tin (Sn) and silver (Ag) than lead (Pb). Therefore, the importance of density is highlighted in selecting the appropriate shielding material.

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